

On the importance of safe practices of mobility evaluation in field-effect transistor and Hall effect measurements of novel materials.

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Proper experimental determination of the charge carrier mobility, μ , is crucial for developing novel electronic devices. In a recent paper, Liu *et al.*^[1] describe perovskite field-effect transistors (FETs) based on solution-coated nanocrystalline CsSnI₃ films, reporting a field-effect mobility $\mu_{\text{FET}} = 55 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, as well as Hall effect measurements of ungated films yielding $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 486 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The authors concluded that they have realized high-performance perovskite FETs. As shown in this Matters Arising, a number of pitfalls of FET and Hall measurements were apparently ignored in this work, leading to erroneous mobility reporting. To help the research community improve the quality of future publications, we propose a *checklist* for Hall measurements designed to minimize errors and inconsistencies.

Inset of **Fig. 1a** reproduces the essential FET data of Liu *et al.* - a semi-log plot of the transfer curve of an “optimized” FET used to extract $\mu_{\text{FET}} = 55 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (their Fig. 1d). We stress that semi-log plots are misleading as they tend to conceal hysteresis, noise, and fluctuations. Thus, we replot the original Fig. 1d to show the double-linear plots of the $I_{\text{SD}}(V_{\text{GS}})$ dependence (**Fig. 1a**) and the corresponding $|I_{\text{SD}}|^{1/2}(V_{\text{GS}})$ dependence used by the authors to extract the saturation mobility of $55 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (**Fig. 1b**). In well-behaved FETs described by the Shockley model, $|I_{\text{SD}}|^{1/2}(V_{\text{GS}})$ in the saturation regime must be linear.^[2-4] Here, the replotted data reveal high hysteresis, significant nonlinearities, and fluctuations. Nevertheless, we can still estimate μ from **Fig. 1** as long as the necessary precautions are taken.

First, μ in disordered semiconductors might be carrier density dependent. Combined with the fact that the gradual channel approximation is violated in the saturation regime,^[2] this makes the evaluation of μ from this regime in disordered FETs unreliable, thus calling for the linear regime measurements.^[4] While Liu *et al.* analyzed their data only using the saturation regime equation, it appears that a significant portion of the transfer curve in **Fig. 1** lies outside of the FET's saturation regime. Indeed, saturation regime in FETs is associated with a pinch-off of the accumulation channel, which occurs when $V_{GS} - V_{TH}$ is between 0 and V_{SD} , where V_{GS} , V_{TH} , and V_{SD} are the gate-source, threshold, and source-drain voltages, respectively.^[2] Note that due to significant self-doping, tin-halide perovskites behave as low carrier density disordered metals,^[5] resulting in high positive threshold (and onset) voltage in CsSnI₃ FETs (inset, **Fig. 1a**). Thus, the portion of the transfer curve at $V_{GS} < V_{SD} + V_{TH} \approx -27.5$ V (to the left of the vertical dashed demarcation line in **Fig. 1a**) is more representative of the linear rather than saturation regime. Estimating μ from this portion yields an average $\mu_{LIN} \approx 13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (**Fig. 1a**).

Second, calculating the saturation mobility from the rest of the curve using the same equation as that used by the authors (Eq. 1 in Liu *et al.*^[1]) yields a strongly fluctuating value with large spikes due to noise and nonlinearities (**Fig. 1b**). Given the nonlinear, highly hysteretic characteristics, attempts to estimate μ in such devices should involve: (a) using the correct saturation regime (here, $V_{GS} > -27.5$ V); (b) employing a linear fit of $|I_{SD}|^{1/2}(V_{GS})$ curve as far from the highly nonlinear subthreshold region as possible, instead of taking advantage of a large peak in $\partial(\sqrt{|I_{SD}|})/\partial V_{GS}$ caused by noise or local nonlinearity; and (c) reporting the mobility reliability factor.^[4] Note that the first evidence that the peak in the apparent mobility at low V_{GS} in FETs is an artifact of gated Schottky contacts and warnings against reporting such "mobilities" were voiced as early as 2011.^[6, 7] It appears that this artifact is general to a variety of FETs.^[4, 8, 9] As shown in **Fig 1b**, the saturation mobility correctly estimated from these data is $\mu_{SAT} \approx 13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

Besides the nonlinear, hysteretic FET characteristics evident from **Fig. 1**, the authors should also be wary of potential non-equilibrium effects caused by astonishingly high Joule power and current densities apparently reached in their FETs (**Fig. 1**): $P^{\max} \approx 180 \text{ W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ and $j_{\text{SD}}^{\max} \approx 200 \text{ kA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (for details, see SI).^[4] To put these values in perspective, this P^{\max} is ~ 500 times greater than the power density emitted by a household iron operating at full power, and this j_{SD}^{\max} exceeds the fusing (melting) safety allowance for a 1 mm-thick solid copper wire by ~ 20 times (SI).^[4] While, in principle, intermittent operation of some FETs at extreme conditions is possible, reporting such measurements requires special care and dedicated control experiments, including *in-situ* monitoring of the actual local temperature of the sample and making sure FET's characteristics are reversible (low hysteresis) and independent of V_{GS} sweep rate. None of these were reported by Liu *et al.*^[1]

These issues are exacerbated by the lack of critical technical details of the Hall measurements. The authors merely listed the extracted Hall mobility and carrier density, but these appear to strongly disagree with their FET measurements. Indeed, there is an enormous inconsistency between the charge carrier density one estimates from the FET characteristics (**Fig. 1a**) and that extracted by the authors from the Hall measurements of the same films. The projected (areal) density, $n_{\text{projected}}$, of mobile holes in doped thin films can be estimated from the positive onset voltage, V_{onset} , of the corresponding FET's transfer curve.^[10-12] At the biasing conditions used by Liu *et al.* (**Fig. 1a**), $n_{\text{projected}} = C_i \cdot V_{\text{onset}}/e \approx 3.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, where $C_i = 34 \text{ nF} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, $V_{\text{onset}} \approx 18 \text{ V}$, and e is the electron charge. Note: although in text-book FETs, $V_{\text{onset}} \approx V_{\text{th}}$, and either value can be used, determination of V_{th} in nonlinear hysteretic FETs is ambiguous, and using V_{onset} for estimating the doped carrier concentration is imperative.^[10-12] Nevertheless, even using $V_{\text{th}} = 12.5 \text{ V}$ listed by the authors would yield similar $n_{\text{projected}}$. Since the thickness of the conducting CsSnI_3 film in this device is $d = 15 \text{ nm}$, the volume carrier density is $n = n_{\text{projected}}/d = 2.5 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At the same time, the reported Hall carrier density for this film is $n_{\text{Hall}} = 3 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (the "optimized" ungated film, also used in the FET in **Fig. 1**). This clearly shows

that there is a *three orders of magnitude* inconsistency between the FET and Hall measurements, with n_{Hall} grossly *underestimated*, likely indicating a flaw in the experiment. Since μ_{Hall} and n_{Hall} are always inversely related ($\mu_{\text{Hall}} \equiv \sigma/en_{\text{Hall}}$, where σ is the film's conductivity), the above inconsistency shows that the reported $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 486 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ is overestimated by three orders of magnitude. Given the lack of experimental details, we abstain from speculating about the origin of this error, but the analysis above shows that the Hall mobility of these samples is likely $\mu_{\text{Hall}} \approx 0.5 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which makes much more sense since μ_{Hall} is expected to be smaller than μ_{FET} in polycrystalline films due to grain boundary effects.^[13, 14]

To minimize artifacts in future publications, we propose the following *checklist* for Hall measurements (for details, see SI): **(a)** perform magnetic field reversal for correct subtraction of spurious Hall voltage background, and/or **(b)** carry out Hall measurements as a function of B field and longitudinal excitation current; **(c)** use four-probe technique for determination of contact-corrected σ ; **(d)** in *ac*-Hall measurements, the frequency dependence must be checked to account for the Faraday induction artifacts;^[15] **(e)** show the exact contact geometry and device architecture; and **(f)** include raw Hall data in publications.

In conclusion, a careful analysis of the data in Liu *et al.*^[1] shows that the reported perovskite FETs are far from ideal, with the correctly estimated μ up to 4 times smaller than the reported value (the reliability factor $r < 30\%$). The reported Hall measurements appear to be deeply flawed, yielding the Hall carrier density and mobility that contradict the FET measurements by 3 orders of magnitude. Using this case as an example, this Matters Arising outlines important safe practices of mobility extraction in FETs and suggests a checklist for Hall measurements universally important for organic, inorganic, or hybrid semiconductors.

Figure 1. Transfer characteristics of the “optimized” CsSnI₃ FET from Liu *et al.*,^[1] replotted here on double-linear plots. In either panel, the vertical dashed line roughly separates the linear and saturation regimes. **(a)** $I_{DS}(V_{GS})$ dependence (green symbols) replotted from the original Fig. 1d of Liu *et al.* reproduced in the inset (the vertical red arrow marks the field-effect onset voltage, V_{onset} , due to self-doping). The derivative, dI_{SD}/dV_{GS} , frequently used to calculate the linear mobility is shown with red symbols and dashed line (see, e.g., Refs. ^[2, 4]). The linear mobility $\mu_{LIN} \approx 13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ is estimated by fitting the linear regime with a linear fit (dashed blue line).^[4] **(b)** The same data replotted as $|I_{SD}|^{1/2}(V_{GS})$ (green symbols). The squared derivative, $(d(|I_{SD}|^{1/2})/dV_{GS})^2$, used by Liu *et al.* to calculate the saturation mobility (Equation 1 in Liu *et al.*^[1]) is shown with red symbols. Since the derivative-based method is not appropriate for noisy and/or nonlinear devices (see text), we have estimated the mobility, $\mu_{SAT} \approx 13 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, by fitting the saturation regime with a linear fit (dashed blue line), while avoiding the sub-threshold nonlinearity around $V_{GS} = 0$.^[4, 6] To be consistent, we used the same branch of the transfer curve (the upper one) as that used by Liu *et al.*

References:

- [1] A. Liu, H. Zhu, S. Bai, Y. Reo, T. Zou, M.-G. Kim, Y.-Y. Noh, "High-performance inorganic metal halide perovskite transistors", *Nat. Electron.* **5**, 78-83 (2022).
- [2] G. Horowitz, "Interfaces in Organic Field-Effect Transistors" in *Advances in Polymer Science*, Vol. 223, *Organic Electronics* (Eds: T. Grasser, G. Meller, L. Li), Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg **2010**, p. 113-153, doi: 10.1007/12_2009_7
- [3] I. McCulloch, A. Salleo, M. Chabinyc, "Avoid the kinks when measuring mobility", *Science* **352**, 1521-1522 (2016).
- [4] H. H. Choi, K. Cho, C. D. Frisbie, H. Sirringhaus, V. Podzorov, "Critical assessment of charge mobility extraction in FETs", *Nat. Mater.* **17**, 2-7 (2018).
- [5] D. B. Mitzi, C. A. Feild, Z. Schlesinger, R. B. Laibowitz, "Transport, Optical, and Magnetic Properties of the Conducting Halide Perovskite CH₃NH₃SnI₃", *J. Solid State Chem.* **114**, 159-163 (1995).
- [6] V. Podzorov, Tutorial Lecture "Organic Single Crystals 101", slides 33-34, Fall MRS 2011 meeting, Boston, MA, USA, Zenodo 2017, doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1048409.
- [7] H. T. Yi, Y. Chen, K. Czelen, V. Podzorov, "Vacuum Lamination Approach to Fabrication of High-Performance Single-Crystal Organic Field-Effect Transistors", *Adv. Mater.* **23**, 5807-5811 (2011).
- [8] C. Liu, G. Li, R. Di Pietro, J. Huang, Y.-Y. Noh, X. Liu, T. Minari, "Device Physics of Contact Issues for the Overestimation and Underestimation of Carrier Mobility in Field-Effect Transistors", *Physical Review Applied* **8**, 034020 (2017).
- [9] C.-S. Pang, R. Zhou, X. Liu, P. Wu, T. Y. T. Hung, S. Guo, M. E. Zaghoul, S. Krylyuk, A. V. Davydov, J. Appenzeller, Z. Chen, "Mobility Extraction in 2D Transition Metal Dichalcogenide Devices—Avoiding Contact Resistance Implicated Overestimation", *Small* **17**, 2100940 (2021).
- [10] E. J. Meijer, C. Tanase, P. W. M. Blom, E. v. Veenendaal, B.-H. Huisman, D. M. d. Leeuw, T. M. Klapwijk, "Switch-on voltage in disordered organic field-effect transistors", *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **80**, 3838-3840 (2002).
- [11] A. R. Völkel, R. A. Street, D. Knipp, "Carrier transport and density of state distributions in pentacene transistors", *Phys. Rev. B* **66**, 195336 (2002).
- [12] A. Benor, A. Hoppe, V. Wagner, D. Knipp, "Electrical stability of pentacene thin film transistors", *Org. Electron.* **8**, 749-758 (2007).
- [13] J. W. Orton, M. J. Powell, "The Hall effect in polycrystalline and powdered semiconductors", *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **43**, 1263-1307 (1980).
- [14] H. H. Choi, A. F. Paterson, M. A. Fusella, J. Panidi, O. Solomeshch, N. Tessler, M. Heeney, K. Cho, T. D. Anthopoulos, B. P. Rand, V. Podzorov, "Hall Effect in Polycrystalline Organic Semiconductors: The Effect of Grain Boundaries", *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **30**, 1903617 (2020).
- [15] Y. Chen, H. T. Yi, V. Podzorov, "High-Resolution ac Measurements of the Hall Effect in Organic Field-Effect Transistors", *Physical Review Applied* **5**, 034008 (2016).

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION:

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1. Reporting voltage sweep rates in measurements of electronic devices.

Electronic devices based on disordered or unstable materials frequently exhibit a substantial dependence of their current-voltage characteristics on the voltage sweep rate.^[1] In perovskite FETs, performing very fast or very slow V_{GS} sweeps or employing V_{GS} pulsed-mode measurements are sometimes strategically used to reduce the apparent hysteresis and maximize the transconductance slope.^[2, 3] It is thus important to explicitly list the gate voltage sweep rates in publications. Furthermore, if a parameter drift or operational instabilities are seen in the measured system, which is frequently the case in metal-halide perovskites, the FET mobility measurements should be performed in a sufficiently wide range of V_{GS} sweep rates. If the dependence of μ on this rate is significant, this dependence should be evaluated and explicitly reported. Unfortunately, Liu *et al.*^[4] have not listed the gate voltage sweep rates used in their study.

2. Inconsistencies in the bulk conductivity of the perovskite films reported by Liu *et al.*^[4]

Tin-halide perovskites usually exhibit a significant self-doping effect, making the samples very conducting (even metallic).^[5] Indeed, Liu *et al.* describe that even their optimized CsSnI_3 films are highly conducting (at zero V_{GS}). For this reason, the authors had to reduce the thickness of the films used in their FETs to $d = 15$ nm, so that the bulk conductivity could be depleted with a positive gate voltage.

From **Fig. 1a** of the main text of this Matters Arising (or the original Fig. 1d of Liu *et al.*), the conductivity of the perovskite film at $V_{GS} = 0$ for the upper branch of $I_{DS}(V_{GS})$ curve is:

$$\sigma_0 \equiv \sigma_{DS}(V_{GS} = 0) = \frac{L}{d \cdot W} \cdot \frac{I_{DS}(V_{GS}=0)}{V_{DS}} = 1.8 \text{ S} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}. \quad (1)$$

This value represents the bulk conductivity of a self-doped 15 nm-thick CsSnI₃ film. However, the Hall effect measurements significantly disagree with this value. Indeed, for the same “optimized” film, the authors report the following (ungated) Hall carrier density and mobility: $n_{\text{Hall}} = 3 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 486 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$. Thus, the bulk conductivity of the film from the Hall measurements is: $\sigma_0 = e \cdot n_{\text{Hall}} \cdot \mu_{\text{Hall}} = 0.23 \text{ S} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$. This nearly an order of magnitude discrepancy between the conductivities of the same sample obtained from the electrical and Hall measurements shows that there is likely an experimental error. Also note that this inconsistency can only become greater (actually, must greater), if one remembers that the (correct) Hall mobility of polycrystalline films is expected to be smaller than their longitudinal FET mobility.^[6]

3. Astonishingly high Joule power and current densities in the FETs reported by Liu *et al.*^[4]

Extremely high Joule power densities are apparently emitted in the channel of FETs reported by Liu *et al.* The maximum value reaches (**Fig. 1** of the main text of this Matters Arising):

$$P^{\text{max}} = \frac{I_{SD}^{\text{max}} \cdot V_{SD}}{W \cdot L} \approx 180 \text{ W} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}, \quad (2)$$

where I_{SD}^{max} is the maximum source-drain current ran through the FET’s channel, V_{SD} is the source-drain voltage, $W = 0.1 \text{ cm}$ and $L = 150 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ are the channel width and length. To put this value in perspective, this P^{max} is ~500 times greater than the power density emitted by a household iron operating at full power (for details, see Ref. ^[7, 8]).

Besides the enormous Joule power densities, the source-drain current densities reached in the channel of these FETs is also astonishing. The maximum current density in the FET’s channel is (**Fig. 1** of the main text of this Matters Arising):

$$j_{SD}^{max} = \frac{\Delta I_{SD}^{max}}{W \cdot t} \approx 200 \text{ kA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}, \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta I_{SD}^{max} = (6.8 - 1) \text{ mA} = 5.8 \text{ mA}$ is the maximum reported gate-induced source-drain current flowing in the FET in addition to the bulk current (the bulk current is $I_{SD}(V_{GS} = 0) \approx 1 \text{ mA}$), $W = 0.1 \text{ cm}$ is the channel width, and $t \approx 3 \text{ nm}$ is the nominal effective thickness of the accumulation channel. Here we take this value of t merely to put our estimates in perspective with similar calculations in other transistors (for details, see Ref. [7, 8]). One should think of this thickness as a parameter used for comparison only. Note, however, that given the total thickness of the perovskite film used in this FET, $d = 15 \text{ nm}$, the lowest physically possible bound of j_{SD}^{max} is not going to be significantly lower than the value calculated above. This current density is mind boggling. For comparison, the fire safety allowance for domestic copper wire (18-AWG, diameter 1.024 mm) at normal conditions is equivalent to $j_{Cu, \text{fire}}^{max} \approx 1.2 \text{ kA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (at this current density, typical plastic insulation of the wiring starts disintegrating and can catch on fire), and its fusing (melting) threshold is $j_{Cu, \text{melting}}^{max} \approx 10 \text{ kA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ (at this current density, a 1 mm-thick solid copper wire is expected to start melting).^[9, 10] This shows that the current density reached in the perovskite material as reported by Liu *et al.* exceeds that causing melting of a thick solid copper wire by ~ 20 times. Note that this estimate provides the lower bound for j_{SD}^{max} reached in these FETs, because our calculation only includes the field-induced current, with the bulk current subtracted, and thus the actual current density is even greater.

We emphasize again that, in principle, operation of semiconductor devices at such extreme biasing conditions is not necessarily in violation of any fundamental laws and might occur under certain experimental conditions or in special measurement regimes, such as, e.g., when heat is very efficiently removed from the sample, or in a very fast, intermittent device operation (a pulsed mode, ultrafast gate voltage sweeps, etc.). However, in such cases, all the details of the measurements should be carefully described, and the necessary control experiments (e.g., monitoring the local temperature of the sample) must also be performed to ensure that the measured transport parameters indeed represent the

equilibrium properties of the semiconductor being investigated. We could not find any of such information in Liu *et al.*^[4], not even V_{GS} sweep rates at which their FET measurements were carried out. As presented, the results appear to imply a regular, *dc* operation of the reported FETs.

4. The *checklist* for Hall effect measurements.

The importance of Hall effect measurements in evaluating the charge carrier mobility of novel materials is being increasingly realized (see, e.g., Ref. ^[7]). However, publications reporting Hall data frequently lack the important control experiments necessary for the reliability of obtained results. We thus suggest the following “*checklist for Hall effect measurements*” to be used by authors and reviewers across subfields. The idea behind it is similar to that adopted by the photovoltaic community.^[11] The importance and urgent need for such a checklist are highlighted by the concerns about the results of the Hall effect measurements reported by Liu *et al.*^[4] and the complete lack of technical details about these measurements in the original article, as described in the main text of this Matters Arising.

(a) Reversal of the magnetic field must be performed for correct subtraction of spurious Hall voltage background. Instruments used in measurements of the Hall voltage may have a non-zero offset that can depend on a number of factors, including the mode of the instrument, properties of the sample, ambient conditions, etc. In addition, non-idealities of the device geometry (e.g., misalignment of the Hall voltage probes) and macroscopic inhomogeneities of the semiconducting material could be sources of potential artifacts. The problem might be exacerbated by the fact that the Hall voltage can be small compared to the longitudinal voltage drop in the device’s channel or the parasitic offset voltage. Considering these issues, the Hall voltage, V_{Hall} , in *dc*-Hall measurements should always be registered in two polarities of the magnetic field, B , and the longitudinal current, I , flowing through the device. That is, B and I should be inverted or nullified to correctly account for zero-level Hall voltage background (the potential difference between the Hall voltage probes independent of the longitudinal

current or the magnetic field).^[12] For instance, reversing the polarity of the B field allows obtaining a background-corrected true Hall voltage:^[12]

$$V_{\text{Hall}}^{\text{true}} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (V_{\text{Hall}}(B^+) - V_{\text{Hall}}(B^-)). \quad (4)$$

(b) In dc -Hall measurements, Hall voltage should be measured as a function of magnetic field and longitudinal excitation current. The portion of the potential difference between the Hall probes truly representing the classical band semiconductor Hall effect (governed by the Lorentz force) and necessary for the determination of the intrinsic charge carrier mobility, μ_{Hall} , of a semiconductor depends linearly on the external magnetic field, B , perpendicular to the channel and the longitudinal excitation current, I : $V_{\text{Hall}} = I \cdot B / en_{\text{Hall}}$, where e is the electron charge, and n_{Hall} is the Hall carrier density. Therefore, both the dependencies, $V_{\text{Hall}}(B)$ and $V_{\text{Hall}}(I)$, are very useful in supporting the reliability of the Hall effect measurements. Thus, experimental verification of the linearity of these dependences is recommended at least for novel systems or systems investigated under uncommon experimental conditions. The magnetic field and longitudinal current should span in such measurements for at least an octave (ideally a decade), also showing the back sweep, so that hysteresis in these dependences can be assessed. The Hall mobility, μ_{Hall} , is obtained from the slope of these linear dependences ($\mu_{\text{Hall}} = \frac{\sigma}{en_{\text{Hall}}} = \frac{V_{\text{Hall}}}{I \cdot B} \sigma$, where σ is the channel conductivity) and should not depend on the specific magnitudes of the magnetic field or excitation current used in the Hall measurements. Thus, linearity of the $V_{\text{Hall}}(B)$ and $V_{\text{Hall}}(I)$ dependences would support a reliable extraction of μ_{Hall} .

(c) The channel conductivity σ should be measured by the four-probe technique to minimize contact related artifacts. Similarly to the importance of the contact-corrected measurements of μ in FETs, four-probe measurements are also important for the extraction of the Hall mobility. The equation for μ_{Hall} given in the section above contains the channel conductivity σ that can also be a source of errors. Thus, four-probe technique is recommended for measurements of σ to avoid errors associated with contact resistance. Importantly, in performing these measurements, one should ensure that the

width of the voltage probes is as small as experimentally possible to minimize inaccuracies due to the *longitudinal channel shunting* effect.^[13]

(d) In *ac*-Hall measurements, the frequency dependence of the Hall mobility must be checked to account for the Faraday induction related artifacts. The Hall effect measurements utilizing an alternating magnetic field with a lock-in detection of the Hall voltage (*ac*-Hall method) are becoming increasingly popular because of their robustness and high sensitivity (high signal/noise ratio), making this technique especially indispensable for investigation of resistive, low-mobility materials. Because it avoids a number of problems associated with *dc*-Hall measurements (including, voltage probe misalignment, high noise, drift of the Hall voltage offset, etc.), the technique can be regarded as the most reliable method for evaluating the Hall mobility. However, as-measured *ac*-Hall voltage can show an apparent dependence on the frequency, f , of the B field. This is related to the Faraday induction e.m.f., V_F , generated in the Hall voltage measuring loop that is proportional to f . Although V_F is phase shifted with respect to the true Hall voltage V_{Hall} by $\pi/2$, both signals can acquire an additional phase shift relatively to the reference signal fed to the lock-in amplifier due to various parasitic capacitances in the measuring and amplification circuit, which will then affect the real component of the net Hall voltage measured by the lock-in.^[14, 15] Thus, in order to extract μ_{Hall} correctly, a zero-frequency offset of the apparent $\mu_{\text{Hall}}(f)$ dependence should be found.^[14] Reporting this frequency dependence in a span of at least one octave would serve to verify the reliable extraction of μ_{Hall} in *ac*-Hall measurements.

(e) Raw Hall data must be included in publications. Similarly to the tradition of presenting raw electrical data, such as transfer or output characteristics, in FET papers, raw experimental Hall data, including the $V_{\text{Hall}}(B, I)$ dependences, the time traces $V_{\text{Hall}}(t)$ recorded as B is swept back and forth between positive and negative values, as well as $\mu_{\text{ac-Hall}}(f)$ in *ac*-Hall measurements, need to be shown at least for representative samples. For example, if van der Pauw contact geometry is used, the Hall voltages (V_{13} , V_{24} , etc.) measured between different pairs of contacts should be shown for various

(positive and negative) magnetic fields and excitation currents. Demonstrating original raw data is considered the gold standard of experimental research, yet a number of authors performing Hall effect measurements of novel materials limit themselves to just listing the extracted transport parameters, without showing raw data, even when their most important conclusions are based on such measurements.^[4]

(f) Sufficiently detailed description of device geometry and (micro)photographs of key devices are necessary. Specific device geometry is very important for verification of conclusions and reproducibility of the reported results. For instance, in a Hall bar geometry, the channel length L , width W , the distance D between the voltage probes along the channel, and the voltage probe width t , are needed to correctly calculate not only the four-probe channel conductivity and the FET mobility but also the Hall mobility and carrier density.^[13] Details of the contact geometry are even more important in the van der Pauw method, where the large size or asymmetry of the contact pads might significantly affect the result.

(g) The device architecture (a cross section) and the origin of mobile charge carriers must be discussed. Analysis of the Hall effect measurements might depend on the source of charge carriers in the sample. The intrinsic charge carrier density in pristine (undoped) wide band-gap semiconductors is usually too low for reliable Hall effect measurements. Hence, charges need to be either injected by an electric field (such as in FETs), photogenerated (photo-Hall effect), or generated in the semiconductor via chemical doping. The origin of charge carriers is very important for understanding the device's properties and measurement reproducibility. For example, in FETs, where the charge transport is interfacial in nature, the mobility is usually affected by the dielectric properties of the gate insulator and the overall quality of the semiconductor-dielectric interface. Nevertheless, sometimes critical information on the architecture of studied devices is missing (as is the case with the Hall measurements reported by Liu *et al.*^[4]), or the origin of mobile charge carriers in the samples is not clearly explained.

References (Supplementary Information):

- [1] Y. Chen, B. Lee, H. T. Yi, S. S. Lee, M. M. Payne, S. Pola, C. H. Kuo, Y. L. Loo, J. E. Anthony, Y. T. Tao, V. Podzorov, "Dynamic character of charge transport parameters in disordered organic semiconductor field-effect transistors", *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14**, 14142-14151 (2012).
- [2] H. P. Kim, M. Vasilopoulou, H. Ullah, S. Bibi, A. E. Ximim Gavim, A. G. Macedo, W. J. da Silva, F. K. Schneider, A. A. Tahir, M. A. Mat Teridi, P. Gao, A. R. b. M. Yusoff, M. K. Nazeeruddin, "A hysteresis-free perovskite transistor with exceptional stability through molecular cross-linking and amine-based surface passivation", *Nanoscale* **12**, 7641-7650 (2020).
- [3] S. P. Senanayak, M. Abdi-Jalebi, V. S. Kamboj, R. Carey, R. Shivanna, T. Tian, G. Schweicher, J. Wang, N. Giesbrecht, D. Di Nuzzo, H. E. Beere, P. Docampo, D. A. Ritchie, D. Fairen-Jimenez, R. H. Friend, H. Sirringhaus, "A general approach for hysteresis-free, operationally stable metal halide perovskite field-effect transistors", *Sci. Adv.* **6**, eaaz4948 (2020).
- [4] A. Liu, H. Zhu, S. Bai, Y. Reo, T. Zou, M.-G. Kim, Y.-Y. Noh, "High-performance inorganic metal halide perovskite transistors", *Nat. Electron.* **5**, 78-83 (2022).
- [5] D. B. Mitzi, C. A. Feild, Z. Schlesinger, R. B. Laibowitz, "Transport, Optical, and Magnetic Properties of the Conducting Halide Perovskite CH₃NH₃SnI₃", *J. Solid State Chem.* **114**, 159-163 (1995).
- [6] H. H. Choi, A. F. Paterson, M. A. Fusella, J. Panidi, O. Solomeshch, N. Tessler, M. Heeney, K. Cho, T. D. Anthopoulos, B. P. Rand, V. Podzorov, "Hall Effect in Polycrystalline Organic Semiconductors: The Effect of Grain Boundaries", *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **30**, 1903617 (2020).
- [7] H. H. Choi, K. Cho, C. D. Frisbie, H. Sirringhaus, V. Podzorov, "Critical assessment of charge mobility extraction in FETs", *Nat. Mater.* **17**, 2-7 (2018).
- [8] H. H. Choi, K. Cho, C. D. Frisbie, H. Sirringhaus, V. Podzorov, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1050699, Zenodo, 2017.
- [9] V. Babrauskas, I. S. Wichman, "Fusing of wires by electrical current", *Conference Proceedings - Fire and Materials 2011, 12th International Conference and Exhibition*, 769-780 (2011).
- [10] American wire gauge, (accessed: November 2022): https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/American_wire_gauge.
- [11] "A checklist for photovoltaic research", *Nat. Mater.* **14**, 1073-1073 (2015).
- [12] V. Podzorov, E. Menard, J. A. Rogers, M. E. Gershenson, "Hall Effect in the Accumulation Layers on the Surface of Organic Semiconductors", *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **95**, 226601 (2005).
- [13] H. H. Choi, Y. I. Rodionov, A. F. Paterson, J. Panidi, D. Saranin, N. Kharlamov, S. I. Didenko, T. D. Anthopoulos, K. Cho, V. Podzorov, "Accurate Extraction of Charge Carrier Mobility in 4-Probe Field-Effect Transistors", *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **28**, 1707105 (2018).
- [14] Y. Chen, H. T. Yi, V. Podzorov, "High-Resolution ac Measurements of the Hall Effect in Organic Field-Effect Transistors", *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **5**, 034008 (2016).
- [15] V. Bruevich, H. H. Choi, V. Podzorov, "The Photo-Hall Effect in High-Mobility Organic Semiconductors", *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **31**, 2006178 (2021).